

WORD-FORMING ASPECT OF COMPUTER SLANG IN INTERNET DISCOURSE

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Abstract. *In this article is considered sources and ways of formation of slang words in the language environment of the Internet.*

Keywords: *Internet user, lexicon, anglicism, computer technologies, language circle, slang, translation, reduction, playful way, sublanguage of programmers, slang reduction, alphanumeric form, adaptation, English-language term, not computer synonym, type of communication.*

In the last decade, communication on the Internet has been especially popular among people of all ages, and especially young people. In our age of global computer technology, this type of communication has become extremely diverse and has both certain advantages and disadvantages.

Internet communication, as a type of communication, was formed not so long ago, but, despite this, it has characteristic features that distinguish it from other types of communication. The language environment of the Internet has led to particularly close attention to the functioning of the Russian language at different levels of its system [1].

The vocabulary of Internet users can also be both literary and non-literary, rarely. But there is also profanity, obscene language, usually expressed in the form of a chaotic set of characters or replacing part of a word with them. According to the philologist, professor of Moscow State University Gasan Huseynov, foul language is inevitable, although it is prosecuted by law as petty hooliganism.

The language of Internet users is also differentiated by age and professional categories, by the level of knowledge of computer technologies, by the interests of users or their preferred activities.

For example, there is a sublanguage of programmers, web designers, systems engineers, hackers, computer gamers, etc. Each group of users is characterized by the use of certain lexical constructions, which may be partially or not familiar to other groups. And only a small part of the language is common to all.

It can be assumed that this part is insignificant compared to the general vocabulary of the Russian language and can hardly affect it in a significant way. In addition, each group of users to varying degrees is characterized by the use of one or another type of vocabulary: slang, jargon, professional terminology, literary language.

The exact share distribution of language types by subgroups is unknown, since such studies have not yet been conducted.

However, the younger generation is more likely to use slang and are familiar with computer terminology. Slang replaces the younger generation with complex linguistic constructions that they have not yet mastered very well.

In addition, young people tend to look for ways to be different from others, to fence themselves off from adult "masters", to have their own secrets, to oppose new game forms to boring traditional foundations, therefore it is they who own most of the linguistic experiments and innovations.

But when the time for games, fun and entertainment fades into the background, you have to master a more businesslike, official literary language, which should replace slang with it.

According to the type of word formation, computer slang and terminology can be divided into the following groups: abbreviations, synonymy, translation, tracing, phonetic mimicry, including game substitution of names with similar words by property or pronunciation, modification or replacement of words for emotional expression, and others.

Most Russian computer terms and slang words are borrowed from foreign languages, more often from English. Their basis is the translation or pronunciation of the relevant concepts.

The following neologisms were formed by fixing their pronunciation by means of Russian graphics: internet (internet), hard drive (Winchester), computer (computer), interface (interface), cursor (cursor), cache (cache), driver (driver), cartridge (cartridge).).

The second group of neologisms arose as a result of the translation of the meaning of the English source word: windows (windows), bookmark (bookmark), background (background), mouse (mouse), basket (basket), keyboard (keyboard), save (save), drag (drag), reboot (reboot, reload, restart).

Some words are formed by abbreviating names, and are often used in this form, for example, VGA, TIFF, VBA, RAM, IP, CD-ROM, HD, DVD, FAT.

Slang abbreviations are more free-form than terms, and established phrases are abbreviated, e.g. known, IMHO (In My Humble Opinion) - In my humble opinion, LOL (Lot Of Laugh) - very funny, I'm dying of laughter, GL (good luck) - good luck. Or the same abbreviations are used, but written in Russian letters, for example, IMHO, LOL, AFAIK, etc.

Often slang abbreviations take an alphanumeric form, replacing syllables with numbers similar in pronunciation, for example, 4GET (Forget) - Forget it, ME2 (Me too) - Me too, 10X (Thanks) - thank you.

It must be said that there are much fewer similar abbreviations formed from Russian phrases and words, since the Internet entered the Russian-speaking space later. Although there are truncated forms of Russian words, for example, computer - computer, programmer - programmer, program - program, robot - bot, register - register, laptop - laptop, beech.

A large number of anglicisms is included not only in modern Russian, but also in other languages. Many technical English terms have appeared in foreign languages as new technologies have been invented in English-speaking countries.

In the United States, for example, the Internet was invented, many of the products of the largest computer manufacturers, which are now becoming transnational, were developed there.

But not only other languages borrow English words, English itself, to a greater extent than other languages, has absorbed tens of thousands of French, Spanish, German, Latin, Greek, Russian and other words [2].

The interaction of languages is growing, perhaps this is some tendency towards the formation of a commonality in languages, interpenetration.

Linguists try to record borrowings and publish them in dictionaries. So, for example, the publishers of the 145,000th Concise Oxford Dictionary of Modern English announce in the preface

that the compilers systematically monitor French, German, Russian and Spanish loanwords in order to catch their entry into a living language in time (for example, “perestroika”, “politburo” or “siloviki”).

There is a three-volume dictionary of anglicisms in German, dictionaries of anglicisms are also published in Russia, for example, the dictionary of M.Yu. Semenova, and in Japanese even a separate alphabet was allocated for writing foreign words.

Many new fashionable words in the Russian language sometimes lead to their unconscious use, to inconsistencies and errors, a large number of which disturb linguists.

Sometimes a mistake seems attractive to society and becomes popular, forming new forms of a word or slang.

This is a well-known phenomenon in linguistics and is called solecism - an irregularity recognized as the norm [3].

For example, “Brothers Grima” is correct, but “Brothers Grimm” is accepted, it is correct to pronounce Es-Sha-A, but they will say “seshea” or simply “usa”.

Often, translators and publishers also offer the public not the most formally correct, but the most convenient and pronounceable spelling of foreign words, for example, office and passport, instead of office and passport, or Manhattan, instead of Manhattan, on purpose, so as not to provoke the stress on the last syllable, as in words Hindustan or Magadan.

The use of slang partly serves to facilitate adaptation to English terms and speed up the process of their implementation.

Much of the slang used on the Internet is designed not only to convey information in a concise and simplified form, but also to enliven it with a humorous tinge.

It is also a playful form of word formation, which gives communication some enthusiasm in order to cheer up, relieve tension, diversify a boring professional conversation, find a common language that contributes to a quick rapprochement and exchange of information.

This is used not only by young people, but sometimes by the adult generation.

The use of such words is often caused by the desire to joke or "speak the same language." So, for example, even a well-known philologist of Moscow State University, in his answers to questions from readers of his blog, instead of “this” writes “sim” with humor, and instead of “maybe” - “mabud” and “should”, in response to a question, one should not whether to greatly simplify the written and spoken language and introduce the Latin alphabet as a second alphabet in order to reduce illiteracy. By the way, the romanization project existed in the time after the October Revolution, but was stopped in the 30s of the XX century.

And now it is widely used without official introduction.

Often the purpose of name substitution is not only humor, but also irony, as well as a manifestation of aggression or rejection, including in relation to an object or a foreign word, for example, winduha, winduza, masdai (Windows), rat-drom (mouse pad), softino (soft, program), muzzle (protective monitor screen), donkey (Internet Explorer browser), autogad (AutoCad). Slang is generally characterized by expressiveness, emotionality, brightness, figurativeness, expressiveness. There can be quite a lot of slang "synonyms" for one concept.

Some words may be replaced by slang due to their similar pronunciation with other words, for example, Bloomers from English shareware - shareware; Soap looks like English. Mail (mail); Firewood - drivers; Mazila - Mozilla browser; Luk, autglyuk - Outlook mail program; Skis - LG;

Quaker - a player in the computer game Quake; Sneakers - KDE; Dolphin is a Delphi programmer; Doomer is a Doom player; Barsik, Vasik - Basic programming language;

Beech - laptop; Avishnik is an avi file.

There are also words formed by turning a modified abbreviated form into a new word, for example:

Windows - Windows; Mother - motherboard; Demo - demo program; Network card - network card; download - download

Different popularity of certain slang words depends on the duration of their use. denote complex phenomena or concepts, such as “sudden suspension of the user’s commands by the computer”, or “starting the necessary computer software”, “software vulnerability”, which did not come up with separate terms, therefore they use similar analogues of existing words.

This is what explains their wide distribution, which goes beyond the Internet, as well as the use of these words in a new meaning to replace non-computer synonyms.

The fashion for other slang words also manifests itself in their frequent use in colloquial speech and the media, but only a few of them become literary and generally accepted.

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